

BUFFERING DELINQUENCY AND CRIME: LITMUS TEST OF JUVENILE JUSTICE

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INTRODUCTION

It's been more than two years when the Rajpath of Lutyen's Delhi was flooded with youth, moved by an unknown anger and almost equally oppressive and confused State Government. The winter of Delhi in 2012 was heated by Candle lights Marches and water cannon beams courtesy Untrained "Men in Uniform". Never in the history of IT in India, the social media has been used for an Unknown Girl, but for an Omnipresent Fear, lived by half of the population, across the globe. "Rape" was at the core of discussion like never before. The Law was amended, the policies were in place, and a swift action by the police lead to the arrest of all the accused and fast tract special court announced the sentence. Death was pronounced for the four convicted persons but not for the youngest one. He was spared because he was few months short of being eighteen.

Though the case is still pending in the court of law, and news channels are

busy discussing the punishment for the juvenile. Almost a year later, 50 years jail imprisonment is announced for a 10 year old boy in Pakistan for murder of a under trail. This article is not an attempt to compare the cold blooded brutal gang rape to spontaneous act of revenge, spreading fire out of gun, nor to go into the psycho-social study of the juvenile, but it is important to do the critical review of the existing Juvenile Justice (JJ) Act present in the country. What does it serve to the therapeutic justice system? What are the basic tenets of JJ Act and recent amendments with respect to Correction Center and Shelter Home? Does it serve any purpose to the behavioral correction?

JUVENILE JUSTICE

The perception of children has changed over a period of time. Initially a child was recognized as a person, but merely as source of pleasure and joy. By the beginning of the 17th century the second idea of

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childhood emerged when the child was perceived as a miniature adult who could be groomed and trained because the belief was that the child was a miniature adult with all the inclinations towards evils and potential for a fallen human nature.¹

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000,² passed to reform the 1986 Act Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Rules, 2007 (as amended in 2011),³ is designed as a comprehensive legal framework by which the Indian government has pledged to alleviate the devastating impact that under development, poverty, and crime have on children. The Act spells out the government's responsibilities in the care, the protection, and the development of neglected children, and also tackles issues related to crime prevention and the rehabilitation of juvenile delinquents. The Act has been formulated in pursuance of the international obligations and standards regarding juvenile offenders. The basic principles under the Beijing rules are: (a) that the reaction to juvenile offenders should always be in proportion to the circumstances of both the offenders and the offence; (b) that the placement of the juvenile in an institution should be a disposition of last resort and for the minimum necessity period; (c) that detention pending trial should be used only as a measure of last resort and for the shortest possible period of time; (d) that police officers dealing with juveniles should be specially instructed and trained.⁴ Surprisingly, the Act has been unable to follow either of the abovementioned principles. Even with the passing of the enactment, child protection in India remains a low priority of the center with an annual allocation of 0.027 per cent of the union budget in 2007-08. The Nithari killings case, from Noida UP, the increasing child trafficking, malnutrition, child labor, girl child neglect all seem to vindicate the

hypothesis that the plight of children in India has remained largely neglected.

DEFICIENCIES IN THE ACT

The preamble of the Act of 2000 and 2007 reads that the Act seeks to amend the law relating to juveniles by providing for proper care, protection and treatment by catering to their development needs, and by adopting a child-friendly approach in the adjudication and disposition of matters in the best interest of children'. Sadly, none of these aims have been fulfilled because of glaring insufficiencies in the Act itself which are not very difficult to point out. Both, in procedural as well as substantive portions, there is a lot that needs to be added to the Act in order that it may actually be useful for the purpose for which it has been established. Some of the very evident loopholes are as following:

USAGE OF THE WORD 'MAY'

A lot of the implementation part has been left up to the States by way of the rules that the States may formulate. The usage of the word 'may' as far as the framing of rules by the States is concerned, it is a major fallacy because until and unless, the formulation of rules is not made mandatory, the implementation of the Act will remain a dream. Section 8 of the Act is an example of the above mentioned problem. According to Section 8 (3) of the Act, the State may formulate rule-and standards for the observation homes that are to be established. Leaving something as important as maintenance of standards to the discretion of the State is a major problem and should be made mandatory for the State to regulate such basic areas.

Even the appointment of inspection committees for the children's homes has been left to the discretion of the States and they 'may' constitute such committees according to Section 29. Something as important as after care organizations, to

check up on the juveniles who have left the special homes and have been adopted or rehabilitated, has also been left to the discretion of the States according to Section.⁴⁴ There are several places in the Act where the usage of the word 'may', which will be disastrous for the implementation of the Act.

EXTENSION OF PERIOD REGARDING INQUIRY

Section 14 says that any inquiry regarding a juvenile, needs to be completed within a period of four months unless there are some special circumstances in special cases. There is absolutely no mention of what the maximum period for inquiry should be and what may be the special circumstances under which the period should be extended. This discretion permits cases to languish in the system indefinitely.⁵ Section 14 gives a lot of scope for arbitrariness and any lack of a judicial attitude on behalf of the juvenile justice board may be sought to be explained as the special circumstances of the cases and hence, they have the option of getting away with it. This is extremely dangerous for a juvenile, in whose case the inquiry should be completed as soon as possible.

PUNISHMENT FOR CRUELTY TO A JUVENILE

According to Section 23, a person responsible for cruelty to a juvenile will be punished with imprisonment for a period of 6 months or with a fine or with both. It is very strange that at a time when the government is trying to curb the menace of cruelty with juveniles, the punishment that they have prescribed is in no way going to act as a deterrent to such erring individuals. The punishment needs to be increased and also the fine amount needs to be specified so that it may discourage the potential law breakers in this area.

SUBSTANTIVE ISSUES

Age: Count Beyond Days

The need to pay attention to empirical research findings on children's cognitive capacities has been largely ignored by policy makers, with an inevitable arbitrariness in legislation. During early adolescence, young people's thinking tends to become more abstract, multi-dimensional, self-reflective and self-aware, with a better understanding of relative concepts. Not only do young people become increasingly able to consider the long term consequences of their actions, they also tend to think about such consequences more in terms of their own sense of responsibility and with increased awareness of the effects of their action on other people.⁶ Overall crime rates, including crime by juveniles, has significantly risen in the past century.⁷

Offenders being children

A nine year old boy earned the dubious tag of being the country's youngest rapist after raping a six year old girl, in Indra, Kangra. Three ten year olds in a Haryana school were booked for molesting a ten year old girl from the same school.⁸ Horrifying incidents like these should force the government to do a rethink on the policies regarding the juvenile offenders.

It is very evident that there is something drastically wrong in the society where such incidents take place. The basic cause of juvenile delinquency and neglect were poverty coupled with lack of parental or societal care, industrialization and slums, bad cinema, substandard education and so on.⁹ First, there are explanations based on individual risk factors as genetic influences, low IQ and poor educational attainment. Secondly, it could be because of changes in living conditions and socio-economic factors. Thirdly it could be based on family and socialization factors, including the influence of mass media.¹⁰ Whatever

may be the reasons for such behavior by children, apart from improving the society and the environment in which the children grow, the fact remains that such children need to be dealt with in a manner that ensures that they do not repeat such acts. Apart from looking into the psychology of such children and getting to the root of the problem, it needs to be ensured that theory of deterrence is used which will discourage the other potential offenders.

Offenders being teenagers

Other than the fact that, the December 16 Nirbhayacase (SC No. 114/2013 FIR No. 413/2012 P.S.: Vasant Vihar, New Delhi) and its verdict which challenged the notions and the legal framework of the JJ Act, a number of other cases grabbed the attention of India. The accused was just few months to completing 18 years of age. The 2007 case of the gruesome murder of a 16 year old boy, Adnan Patrawala, by his teenaged friends, who later pleaded delinquency is a very important case as far as the importance of age is concerned. In a very recent case of a similar kind, a 17 year old boy was kidnapped and killed by his close friends for money.¹¹ Section 2 (k) of the Act has defined a juvenile as anyone below 18 years of age. This Section will protect the offenders in the abovementioned cases because they were below the age of 18 years.

The logic behind the existence of the Act was to protect the juveniles because they were not supposed to have the necessary mental element required to commit crimes. This is the reason behind having milder laws and punishments to deal with juvenile offenders. However, in the abovementioned cases, it is very evident that the offenders had the necessary knowledge and mental element regarding the commission of the crime. During the debate regarding the Act, Shrimati Lakhanpal said that the problem of delinquent children 'is a difficult one and not understandable for all. The tendency of

these children is corrupt, morbid and quite different from the ordinary ones. They have extraordinary leanings for crime. It is an essential though difficult task to make them good citizens.¹² It is not fair that an offender of 19 years of age get life imprisonment for a murder while an individual of 17 years of age gets away with a minor punishment.

Need for the Policy of Waiver

In the Nirbhaya's Case,¹³ other than that socio-economic condition, which anyway, does not justify the gruesome act, was overlooked along with the peer group he (accused) owned. In the Reepak Ravindran 14 case, the 15 year old boy was convicted for rape of a 7 year old girl. The fact that the boy was working in a lodge where he was exposed to act of adults, and blue films while serving guests were considered as mitigating circumstances leading to the commission of offence. Even if the crime is shocking to the conscience and the conduct abhorring, still Section 22, being aware of it, provides for keeping them in safe custody.¹⁵ In case the offence was serious or the child is of depraved nature, the courts suggested that the appropriate course for the juvenile courts was to send the matter to the government¹⁶ for deciding the term of detention.¹⁷

The concept of waiver has been extensively used in the United States of America. There exists an underlying acceptance that juveniles who engage in felonious offences should be treated as adults, because the harm to society committed by youths is identical to harm committed by adults.¹⁸ There are three kinds of waiver-legislative waiver, judicial waiver and prosecutorial-waiver. In case of legislative waiver, the legislature excludes certain crimes from the jurisdiction of the juvenile court. Some crimes such as murder, rape, etc. are so severe that no leniency should be shown to the offenders. In judicial waiver, the juvenile court judge has the discretion to waive of the

jurisdiction of the juvenile court keeping in mind the nature of offence, age of offender and the past record of the juvenile. The same powers are given to the prosecutor in case of prosecutorial waiver.¹⁹ In most states judges decide whether a youth is a criminal or a delinquent in a waiver hearing and base their discretionary assessments on a juvenile's 'amenability to treatment' or 'dangerousness'.²⁰ Legislatures increasingly use age and offence criteria to redefine the boundaries of adulthood, coordinate juvenile transfer and adult sentencing practices, and reduce the 'punishment gap'.²¹ There are some juveniles who are extremely dangerous to others and who do not appear to be amenable to rehabilitation. Most of the states have established mechanisms for transferring or waiving jurisdiction to adult courts in such cases.²² India needs to include something on the lines of waiver in the Act in order to take care of juveniles committing serious offences and also in cases where the juvenile is a teenager and well aware to understand the implications of his act. An assessment of a minor's level of competency should constitute the first legal decision so decide the manner in which the minor should be treated. To promote a more coherent juvenile justice policy, and to permit alternatives to the current system to be implemented, a different rhetoric should be developed, based on the competency and responsibility of individual juveniles.²³

THE JUVENILE JUSTICE (CARE AND PROTECTION OF CHILDREN) AMENDMENT ACT, 2011

In order to meet the implementation challenges this is an Act further to amend the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000. As enacted by Parliament in the Sixty-second Year of the Republic of India as Short title and commencement.

1. This Act may be called the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Amendment Act, 2011. It come into force on such date as the Central Government notified in the Official Gazette, appoint.
2. Amendment of Section 48 - In the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000 (56 of 2000) (Hereinafter referred to as the principal Act), in Section 48, Sub-Section (2) shall be omitted.
3. Substitution of new Section for Section 58-For Section 58 of the principal Act, the following Section shall be substituted, namely:—
 58. (1) Where it appears to the competent authority that any juvenile or child kept in a special home or an observation home or a children's home or a shelter home or in an institution in pursuance of this Act, is a mentally ill person or addicted to alcohol or other drugs which lead to behavioral changes in a person, the competent authority may order his removal to a psychiatric hospital or psychiatric nursing home in accordance with the provisions of the Mental Health Act, 1987 (14 of 1987) or the rules made thereunder.
 - (2) In case the juvenile or child had been removed to a psychiatric hospital or psychiatric nursing home under sub-section (1), the competent authority may, on the basis of the advice given in the certificate of discharge of the psychiatric hospital or psychiatric nursing home, order to remove such juvenile or child to an Integrated Rehabilitation Centre for

Addicts or similar centres maintained by the State Government for mentally ill persons (including the persons addicted to any narcotic drug or psychotropic substance) and such removal shall be only for the period required for the inpatient treatment of such juvenile or child.

Explanation - For the purposes of this Sub-Section -

- (a) "Integrated Rehabilitation Centre for Addicts" shall have the meaning assigned to it under the scheme called "Central Sector Scheme of Assistance for Prevention of Alcoholism and Substance (Drugs) Abuse and for Social Defense Services" made by the Government of India in the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment or any other corresponding scheme for the time being in force;
- (b) "mentally ill person" shall have the meaning assigned to it in clause (l) of Section 2 of the Mental Health Act, 1987 (14 of 1987);
- (c) "psychiatric hospital" or "psychiatric nursing home" shall have the meaning assigned to it in clause (q) of Section 2 of the Mental Health Act, 1987 (14 of 1987).

PROCEDURAL ISSUES

More than the substantive issues, it is the procedural issues that have played

spoilsport for the Act. Lack of properly trained officials and allocation of proper funds have been the responsible for the widespread violations of the Act. Judicial officers are not used to being overshadowed by social workers while dealing with persons committing offences, nor are the social workers familiar with the idea that their opinion counts as much as that of the Magistrate's. In addition, the Magistrates usually do not have an occasion to acquire special knowledge of child psychology and welfare, which is an essential qualification under the Act, before being appointed to the Board.²⁴ Social workers need to know the laws applicable to children lest the Magistrates subdue them. The members of the Committee, too, need to know the scheme and provisions of the Act under which they operate. Complete knowledge regarding the various laws applicable to the juveniles is required. Special training of police officers in each police station is essential for the special juvenile/child welfare officers and special juvenile police units in each district to discharge their duties effectively.²⁵ Rather than avoiding harm, police interactions with juveniles tend to involve abusive interrogation techniques, sometimes bordering on torture.

JURISPRUDENTIAL ANALYSIS

Two distinct reasons compel a re-examination of juvenile justice jurisprudence:

1. There does exist systems where either juvenile justice has not fully evolved, or a common understanding of the concept is lacking.
2. Even in advanced countries serious doubts and rethinking is under way in the field that is manifest in the process of "Recriminalizing Delinquency" and measures like juvenile justice jurisdiction, waiver provisions and statutes.²⁶

The Convention on the Rights of the Child provides an elaborate catalogue of children's rights that can be grouped into four main categories:

- Right to Survival
- Right to Protection
- Right Participation, and
- Right to Development

The rights impose obligations not only on the State, but also on parents and the community, which means a change in approach: from kindness and charity to children to moral and legal obligations to them.²⁷ However this system has come in for criticism because like the needs of the children, their rights are also a creation of the adult institutions, in which children have no say even though they have a positive contribution in the construction of their own lives and in the lives of others. Applying John Rawls' theory of justice, which is about equality of opportunity and the difference principle,²⁸ it would be perfectly in order not to grant to children same liberty rights as adults, but they ought to be accorded protection rights and rights based on needs.²⁹ Therefore, all children should be provided with resource and opportunities that will allow them to develop their freedom since not being able to participate effectively in taking choices that governs one's life would be a capability deprivation since both material and political control over one's environment is a central human capability.³⁰

Essentially, there are three components to the juvenile justice system:

1. Identify the patterns of thinking that have led the child to perform acts of crime and violence in the past and that pose a risk of such behaviors in the future;
2. Learn specific skills for intervening in and controlling these patterns of thinking; and

3. Summarize these patterns and interventions in the form of a plan for controlling their high-risk thinking in the community.³¹

CONCLUSION

The story of the Juvenile Justice Act is one of broken promises and dashed hopes.³² Passing of the Bills without the necessary resources is merely eyewash as implementation is the crux of the matter.³³ The general quality of juvenile justice remains coarse and arbitrary with little regard for fairness and justness to the juvenile concerned.³⁴ Though the concept of juvenile justice comprises two important ideas, viz., fairness or justness to children and alternative standards of administering justice, there is preoccupation with the second idea due to the utilitarian grounds of serving the public.³⁵

As of now, the Government of India has made a serious note of the Justice Verma Committee Report that will hopefully offer solutions to the present problems. The Ministry of Women and Child Development is creating Model Rules as an addendum to the Juvenile Justice Act, with the intention that all states will adopt and comply with them. These rules will hopefully take care of all the inadequacies of the Act, and will provide for set guidelines regarding the implementation of the Act. The Ministry is also overhauling the Department of Women and Child's organizational structure and policy, creating an Integrated Child Protection Scheme ("ICPS"). The Rules advocate for a stronger relationship between NGOs and government agencies, an acknowledgement of the positive impact NGOs can have within the Observation Homes and throughout the system. The Integrated Child Protection Scheme will hopefully address implementation concerns, through an entirely new bureaucratic structure and increased expenditures for child protection.

Three different justifications have been advanced for a separate juvenile system:³⁶

- (1) compared to adults, children are more treatable;
- (2) compared to adults, children are less culpable; and
- (3) compared to adults, children are less deterrable.

All these criteria need to be utilized to ensure that the objective of the separate juvenile justice-system is fulfilled. It has been discovered that deterrence-based interventions do not have the requisite effects on children and it is therefore better to go in for reformatory justice. In order to have effective functioning of the juvenile justice system, there must be close coordination between police, magistracy and social services. The involvement of NGO's in the juvenile justice system is a boon as they seem to be more aware of ground realities and problems facing the children.³⁷ Mental health and juvenile justice systems must work together to address the psychological components of rehabilitating delinquent youth. The therapeutic jurisprudence, which lies in the use of community based programs for the mentally ill juvenile offenders, needs to be applied in the juvenile justice system.³⁸ Fairness and justness to children does not only demand that their liability ought to be diminished, but also ordains that they must be subject to protective and restorative measures as are most conducive to their reintegration into the society.³⁹ It needs to be ensured that the child does not end up getting the worst of both the worlds; he gets neither the protections accorded to adults nor the solicitous care nor regenerative treatment postulated for children.⁴⁰

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